

CERTAIN ASPECTS OF HYDROGEN PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION IN A REFINERY

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Keywords: Hydrogen, Steam methane reforming, Equilibrium constant, Approach to equilibrium, Combined steam and power plant, Pressure swing adsorption, Refinery offgases

Abstract

Steam methane reforming (SMR) process is the most important hydrogen source in SLOVNAFT refinery. Being a large natural gas consumer and important heat exporter, its operation mode and efficiency influences the whole refinery. In case its debottlenecking is to be considered, an adiabatic pre reformer installation can be considered among other options. In order to correctly calculate and analyze the corresponding benefit, the authors firstly dealt with the newer SMR plant design state verification and recalculation. It has been shown that taking into account the "approach to equilibrium" parameter is crucial to assess the underlying material and heat balances. Its design values are around 20 °C for radiation section and 8 to 10 °C for the high-temperature shift reactor which reflects the conservative approach of the plant vendor to process guarantees. Further process investigation is considered with the aim to set the plant operation efficiency properly into the wider scope of energetic media consumption of the whole refinery.

1 Introduction

Hydrogen production and consumption efficiency belongs to factors crucial for the economics of a standard refinery. Depending on the local conditions, various sources of hydrogen can be cost effective, however, as is generally acknowledged [1,2], Steam methane reforming (SMR) process is usually at the same time both the most important and marginal hydrogen source.

It seems to become even more important due to more stringent EU regulations on the aromatics content in gasoline, whereby another important hydrogen source – Gasoline catalytic reforming (CCR) process – becomes less favorable for gasoline octane number increase [2]. Other hydrogen sources like Steam cracker (SC), and hydrogen separation from refinery offgases (ROGs), including Pressure swing adsorption (PSA) offgases, contribute to lesser extent to the refinery's hydrogen pool.

Another important factor is the produced hydrogen quality. Following Tab. 1 presents the average hydrogen content and other basic facts about various hydrogen streams produced in SLOVNAFT refinery. Their purity and available pressure shapes the limits of their universality in various hydrocracking and hydrogenation processes in the refinery. The CCR hydrogen is thus preferentially consumed in processes with lower hydrogen cycle gas purity, like Vacuum gasoil hydrotreater, Isomerisation and in some older hydrogenation units.

The SMR feedstock (natural gas and ROGs) preparation comprises its compression and preheat in convection section of the reformer furnace, desulphurization over the fixed bed of ZnO, mixing with process steam and further preheat in the convection section. The mixture then

passes through catalysts-filled tuber in the radiation section of the furnace, where the major part of hydrogen is produced by a two step equilibrium reaction (1,2):

Higher hydrocarbons present in the natural gas and in the ROGs are fully converted to methane, CO and CO₂. In case the ROGs can be alternatively processed in an independent separation unit to yield high purity hydrogen and fuel gas, the economics of both alternatives has to be examined properly, as presented in [3].

Tab. 1 Key facts about hydrogen sources in SLOVNAFT refinery. ROGs treatment #2 is under commissioning.

Hydrogen source	SMR process	Steam cracker	CCR	ROGs treatment #1	ROGs treatment #2
H ₂ purity, % v/v	>99.9	70	95	>99.9 (PSA process)	90 to 93 (membranes)
Impurities	ppms	Methane, traces of C ₂	C1 to C5 hydrocarbons, ppms of Cl ₂ and HCl	ppms	C1 to C5 hydrocarbons, nitrogen
Available at pressure, MPa	2 to 2.2	4	3.3	1.5	2.4 after recompression
Typical share on SLOVNAFT's H ₂ pool, %	50 to 60 (2 SMR plants together)	5 to 10	≈ 30	≤ 3	≈ 5

The mixture is partly cooled down and in a high-temperature shift reactor additional hydrogen is produced by the further (2) reaction that benefits from lower temperature than in the radiation section. The reactor outlet is further cooled down to ambient temperature, whereby the unreacted water steam is condensed and the dry gas enters the PSA unit. Its major product is the high purity hydrogen and the PSA offgas. The PSA unit efficiency in terms of high purity hydrogen stream flow to total hydrogen in the PSA unit inlet usually exceeds 85 %. The PSA offgas is mixed with natural gas and is used as fuel in the reformer furnace. Heat provided by reaction mixture cooling and recovered excess heat in the convection section of the furnace are used for high (3.5 MPa) and low (0.5 MPa) pressure steam production and for boiler feedwater preheating and deaeration for own consumption and for export to adjacent units. The process steam condensate is collected, stripped from the absorbed CO₂ in the stripper (desorption column) and reused for steam production.

A standard SMR unit is a net heat exporter, thus any changes in its operation and efficiency have the impact on the refinery's steam network and consequently on the marginal steam source. In the case of SLOVNAFT refinery, the marginal steam source is the Central steam and power plant (CSPP) that produces very high pressure steam (9 MPa) from liquid fuel and cogenerates electric energy in a set of backpressure and extraction-condensing steam turbines.

Hydrogen production cost may therefore be calculated by taking into account [2-4]:

- Feedstock (natural gas and ROGs) and auxiliary fuel (natural gas) cost
- Credit in the net exported high and low pressure steam
- Cost of electric energy consumed in the SMR process
- Loss of cogenerated electric energy in case of decreased steam export from the CSPP

In a standard refinery in case of rising hydrogen demand, the SMR process is suitable candidates for debottlenecking. Apart from operational adjustments (reaction pressure and temperature optimization, water steam to feed ratio optimization) and PSA unit enlargement, other options are available:

1. Adiabatic prereformer installation. The mixture of feedstock and water steam passes through a catalyst-filled adiabatic reactor prior entering the radiation section of a reformer furnace. In such reactor, all C₂ and heavier hydrocarbons are converted to methane, CO and CO₂, thus it enables to produce hydrogen also from heavier hydrocarbons (f.e. gasolines) that does the conventional MR process design allow. Moreover, it somewhat decreases the heat load in the radiation section, thus the net steam export from the SMR plant is decreased.
2. Countercurrent prereformer installation. In this alignment, the heat for feedstock prereforming is provided by cooling the radiation section outlet mixture. The effects of widened feedstock processing possibility and steam export decrease are comparable to 1.
3. Partial CO₂ removal from the reaction mixture prior to entering the PSA unit. Usually this is done in a caustic solution scrubber; the rich solvent being regenerated by water steam stripping in a stripping column and its head product being a CO₂ rich gas suitable for expedition or for CO₂ sequestration process.

From the numerous factors influencing hydrogen consumption in a refinery, one can mention crude quality, products spectrum, technology age or hydrogen cascading, where the hydrogen-rich off gases from one unit is used as make up hydrogen for another one with lower hydrogen purity demands. Thereby less hydrogen ends in the lower quality off gases and is burned in refinery furnaces as fuel. If there is demand for hydrogen recovery from these off gases, one must carefully calculate the processing costs, including among others large portion of compression work. Even more importantly one must not forget that the lower heating value of hydrogen is approximately 2.4 times higher than that of middle European quality [5] natural gas, thus the recovered hydrogen must be replaced by adequate amount of other fuel in order to keep the refinery's fuel gas network balanced.

2 Aims of the contribution

From the numerous factors coupled with hydrogen production and consumption efficiency due to limited space of this contribution we focus at the analysis of reaction mixture composition at the reformer furnace and HT-shift reactor exits using SLOVNAFT's HPP2 (the newer Hydrogen production plant) design data.

3 Applied methodic

Scheme of the HPP2 plant is provided in the Fig 1. The design state analysis dealt with comparison of calculated and design reaction mixture composition in the calculation points I. and III. as well as with heat consumption in the furnace radiation section. Further calculations comprising adiabatic pre reformer with additional heat exchanger section in the furnace convection section dealt mainly with reaction mixture composition in the calculation point V and estimation of heat consumption decrease in the furnace radiation section.

The calculations themselves included:

1. Material and heat balances; using ideal gas enthalpies, based on temperature dependences of specific heat capacities obtained from [6].
2. Equilibrium constants K_a for reactions (1,2), based on common physico-chemical relations, calculating the reaction Gibbs energies

$$K_{a1} = K_{x1} \cdot \left(\frac{p}{p^o} \right)^{\sum v_i} = \frac{x_{CO} \cdot x_{H_2}^3}{x_{CH_4} \cdot x_{H_2O}} \cdot \left(\frac{p [kPa]}{101.325 kPa} \right)^2 = e^{\frac{\Delta_r G_1}{RT}} = e^{\frac{\Delta_r H_1 - T \Delta_r S_1}{RT}} \quad (3)$$

$$K_{a2} = K_{x2} \cdot \left(\frac{P}{P^o} \right)^{\sum v_i^2} = \frac{x_{CO2} \cdot x_{H2}}{x_{CO} \cdot x_{H2O}} = e^{\frac{\Delta_r G_2}{RT}} = e^{\frac{\Delta_r H_2 - T \Delta_r S_2}{RT}} \quad (4)$$

By combining both calculation steps we were able to calculate the equilibrium reaction mixture composition as well as heat balance and temperatures in the calculation points. The underlying design parameters are summed up in the Tab 2.

Tab. 2 Design parameters for the HPP2 plant relevant to this study. Design parameters for all design cases: temperatures $T_{I.}$, $T_{II.}$: 850 and 360 °C; $T_{III.}$: see Table 4; $p_I.$ = 2.78 MPa (g). NG design quality: methane content 97.4 % mol and NG molar mass 16.53 kg/kmol.

Design case	NG feed; suppl. NG, t/h	ROGs feed, t/h	ROGs M, kg/kmol; H ₂ content, % mol	Steam to feed mass flow ratio	Inlet radiation section temperature, °C	$x_{CH_4, I.}$; $x_{CO, III.}$, % mol on dry basis	Heat consumed in radiation coils, MW
NG only	11.337; 1.601	0	-	3.3	520	7.27; 3.05	43.278
NG + ROGs #1	7.855; 1.47	3.415	19.36; 37.0	3.21	515	7.16; 3.13	41.902
NG + ROGs #2	6.401; 1.075	4.697	14.13; 55.77	3.3	510	7.32; 3.13	40.028

Fig. 1 Schematic depiction of the main HPP2 material streams. I. to V.: computation points. HX = heat exchanger.

4 Obtained results and their analysis

Results of design cases recalculations are provided in Tab 3,4. The primary recalculations took into account the exact values of design parameters (temperatures, pressure, feed composition) and assumed reaching equilibrium reaction mixture composition both at the outlet of radiation coils and HT-shift reactor. The obtained values of reaction mixture composition, heat consumption in the radiation coils and net H₂ production highlighted in the Tab 3,4 do not match with the corresponding design values. As appears from their comparison, the design

parameters yielded higher conversions of methane and consequently higher heat consumption in radiation coils and higher hydrogen production than resulted from hypothetical equilibrium conditions. At first glance this appears unrealistic, as the design methane conversion should be below the hypothetical ones. On the contrary the HT-shift calculations yielded higher than design CO conversion which complies with real behavior expectance.

Tab. 3 Results of HPP2 design states recalculations – radiation section

Design case recalculation	Calculated based on design T_I and p_I values		Calculated based on design T_I and p_I values; with optimized reaction temperature in radiation coils		
	$x_{CH_4,I}$, % mol on dry basis calc./design	Heat consumed in radiation coils, MW calc./design	Optimized reaction temperature, °C	$x_{CH_4,I}$, % mol on dry basis calc./design	Heat consumed in radiation coils, MW calc./design
NG only	8.84 / 7.27	41.22 / 43.28	871.9 for both (1), (2)	7.27 / 7.27	43.25 / 43.28
NG + ROGs #1	9.28	38.9 / 41.9	878.1 for (1) 850 for (2)	7.16 / 7.16	41.40 / 41.90
NG + ROGs #2	8.95	37.7 / 40.02	872.3 for both (1), (2)	7.32 / 7.32	39.73 / 40.02

Tab. 4 Results of HPP2 design states recalculations – HT shift and net H₂ export. * - Applied PSA design efficiency equal to 87 %; pure hydrogen basis

Design case recalculation	Calculated based on design T_I , T_{II} and p_I values			Calculated based on design T_I , T_{II} and p_I values; with optimized reaction temperature in radiation coils and in the HT shift reactor		
	$x_{CO,III}$, % mol on dry basis calc./design	T_{III} , °C calc./design	Net exported H ₂ , t/h* calc./design	Optimized HT shift reaction temperature, °C	$x_{CO,III}$, % mol on dry basis calc./design	Net exported H ₂ , t/h* calc./design
NG only	2.51 / 3.05	419.0 / 422	3.25 / 3.437	431.5	3.05 / 3.05	3.439 / 3.437
NG + ROGs #1	2.64 / 3.13	421.5 / 424	3.20 / 3.437	423.7	3.13 / 3.13	3.445 / 3.437
NG + ROGs #2	2.49 / 3.05	419.2 / 422	3.26 / 3.437	430.7	3.13 / 3.13	3.445 / 3.437

The explanation of the seemingly different results of the methane and CO conversion lies beforehand: In the radiation section, heat is transported from hot flue gas through the walls to the internal space of the radiation tubes. As the tubes are filled with catalyst, heat transfer inside of them is firstly realized by conduction through the catalyst particles and only thereafter from the catalyst particles surface to the gaseous reaction mixture. This holds true despite the fact that the final reaction heat effect is strongly endothermic. Thus we can suppose the active catalyst sites to have at least 20 to 40 °C higher temperature than is the design outlet temperature (850 °C). This effect cannot be separated from that of catalyst activity that on the contrary generally yields lower than equilibrium conversion. The resulting combined effect is summed up in the “approach to equilibrium” [7] parameter that, according to catalysts manufacturers, usually varies in the range of 5 to 20 °C and represents the difference between the hypothetical reaction

mixture temperature that yields equilibrium composition equal to the real one and the real outlet temperature. The results shown in the Tables 3,4 corroborate this: the optimized (hypothetic) reaction temperature is by cca 21 °C higher than the design one. The same effect can be seen in the HT-shift reactor as well, where a weak exothermic reaction takes place on the catalyst surface. The optimized (hypothetic) HT-shift reaction temperature lays above the outlet one by 8 to 10 °C.

By employing optimized reaction temperatures in our calculations, we reached an excellent match between design and calculated reaction mixture composition, heat consumption in radiation tubes and net hydrogen production. It must however be remarked that the above statements do not apply to the NG + ROGs #1 design state, where the optimized reaction temperature for methane conversion is higher than those for other two design states but that for CO reaction matches with the real one both in the radiation tubes and the HT-shift. We cannot reasonably explain these discrepancies at present.

5 Conclusions

The Steam methane reforming process belong both to crucial and very energy-intense processes in a refinery as it usually provides the majority of hydrogen production capacity. If a debottlenecking of this process is desired, one might examine the possibility of an adiabatic pre reformer installation that enables both heavier than traditional feedstock utilization and can bring about a moderate cut in the furnace's fuel consumption requirement.

Calculations focused on the verification of the newer Hydrogen production plant in SLOVNAFT refinery design operational cases demonstrated the necessity to take into account the “approach to equilibrium” parameters both for radiation section and the HT-shift, whereby an excellent match between the design and calculated process parameters could be achieved.

The authors intent to deal with the Steam methane reforming process analysis more deeply and in context with the energetic media consumption in the whole refinery and publish their findings in a dedicated scientific paper.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to express their gratitude to all SLOVNAFT refinery employees, involved in this study for their support and hope for further fruitful cooperation.

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